

Research Article

An Evaluation of the Implementation of the Senior High School Sports Track Program in Public Secondary Schools in National Capital Region: Implication For Enhancement

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Abstract: The study focused on the evaluation in the extent of implementation in the Senior High School Sports Track Program of DepEd–NCR using CIPP Evaluation Model. The Program is one of the new features in the Philippine Basic Education, Senior High School. The program was evaluated using the model's four sections of: Context, Input, Process, and Product. Context evaluation serve to identify the extent of implementation of the program goals and objectives of the SHS Sports Track, Input evaluation serves to determine the extent of implementation of the program plan in terms of internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (partner and linkages) and administrative support, process evaluation serves to identify the extent of implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies and Product evaluation serves to determine the extent of implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum, work immersion program and seven (7) specialized courses. The study was conducted using the descriptive research design. It involves four sets of respondents with their different view of perspective in the extent of the program. The program was only in the third year of implementation and this is the first evaluation made. Through the findings and conclusions of the study, recommendations for the program enhancement were developed. The findings may utilize by the Department of Education for the enhancement of the Sports Track Program implementation.

Keywords: sports track program, senior high school, CIPP model of evaluation.

Introduction

The Philippines had recently faced a major reform in its educational system by improving the curriculum and spreading the number of learning years from a 10-year to a 13-year basic education system. Two years ago, the Philippines was the only country in Asia and one of the three remaining countries in the world with a 10-year basic education system (Giron, 2012). Other countries require a 12-year basic education before entering the tertiary level. For example, the Washington Accord which was signed in 1989 required a minimum of 12-year basic education for recognition of engineering professionals. Likewise, the Bologna Process (1999) requires a minimum of 12-year basic education for students to be admitted in universities and practice their profession in European countries. The Implementation of the K-12 Program addressed the two-year gap of international standards. It features the universal Kindergarten (K), Elementary education (6 years), Junior High School (4 years) and the additional Senior High School (2 years). The two additional years will provide longer and enough time for students to master the lessons against the congested content curriculum of the 10-year Basic Education Program. According to the Department of Education (DepEd), graduates of Senior High School are expected to be more prepared for work and/or later pursue a college degree (Order no. 43, s. 2013).

The legal bases for the establishment of a Senior High School Sports Track Program in the Philippines is stated in Section 4, paragraph (a) of Republic Act (RA) No. 10533 otherwise known as the “Enhanced Basic Education of 2013”:

The enhanced basic education program encompasses at least one (1) year of kindergarten education, six (6) years of elementary education, and six (6) years of secondary education, in that sequence. Secondary education includes four (4) years of junior high school and two (2) years of senior high school education. Kindergarten education shall mean one (1) year of preparatory education for children at least five (5) years old as a prerequisite for Grade 1. (RA 10533)

DepEd stated that with RA 10533 the 21st century core skills needed in order for Filipino learners to be globally competitive and to be functionally literate will be met. The solution was to add two more years to the basic education system, the Senior High School (SHS). The SHS includes two years of specialized upper secondary education and students have the option to choose a specialization based on their aptitude, interests, and school capacity.

Their SHS *career track* will define the content of the subjects they will have to take which will fall under either the core curriculum or specialized tracks. The SHS program is the realization of Section 2, paragraph (b) of RA 10533:

Broaden the goals of high school education for college preparation, vocational and technical career opportunities as well as creative arts, sports and entrepreneurial employment in a rapidly changing and increasingly globalized environment. (RA 10533)

DepED Order no. 51, s. 2015 *Guidelines of Implementation of Senior High School Program in Existing Public Junior High School and Integrated Schools, Establishment of Stand-Alone Public Senior High School and Conversion of Existing Public Elementary and JHSs Into Stand Alone SHSs*, contains the guidelines and steps in applying permit to offer Senior High School Program in schools, as well as the checklist of facilities that should be available and accessible aligned to the track plan to be offered:

The present Philippine SHS model, the student can choose among four tracks, namely: (1) Academic; (2) Technical-Vocational-Livelihood; (3) Sports; and (4) Arts and Design. The *Sports Track* is one of the new features in the Philippine SHS Basic Education. It allows students who are sports aligned an opportunity to *compendium* their skills in the field and prove themselves that sports is not only a hobby but a possible future profession. It also gives teachers, who are majors in Physical Education and Sports, with specialized skills to use and to share their expertise.

Stipulated in the DepEd Order no. 25, s. 2105 *Implementing Guidelines on the Special Program in Sports*, the program also has a paradigm shift in terms of its objectives; it envisions to equip the SPS students for employment or higher learning in field of sports and related areas.

The Sports Track Program in SHS ideally is the catch basin of students who graduated from the SPS. For instance, the sector of Philippine education gives attention to the sports, physical education and health as a job opportunity through offering Sports Track Program in Senior High School.

Sports Track Program aims to make students understand and possess the basic knowledge in sports, skills and prepare the students in a career that is related to physical education and sports. It also offers the students learning various factors that affect social, psychological, and cognitive development in sports leadership and management. Part of the curriculum in the Sports Track is Safety and First Aid. This is to ensure that students have the life skills and competencies in safety, injury prevention and management in various sports and exercise settings for prompt and proper response during emergencies. It is designed to produce quality Filipino graduates that will be aligned

in physical education, first aid, fitness, recreation and sports. On the other hand, fitness trainers, game officials, tournament manager, recreation attendant, masseur, or gym instructor are the profession related to this track. The most beneficial result from enrolling in the program is to understand the basic principles and techniques in relation to physical education and recreation and inject to them the various factors that affect social, psychological, and cognitive development in sports leadership and management.

Research Objectives

The study evaluates the implementation of the Senior High School Sports Track by the Department of Education in the National Capital Region.

Specifically, it sought the following sub problems: What is the extent of answers to implementation of the program goals and objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program? What is the extent of implementation of the Program Plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (Partner and Linkages) and administrative support? What is the extent of implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies? What is the extent of implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum, work immersion program and seven (7) specialized courses? And lastly, based on the result of the study, what implications can be given to enhance the implementation of Senior High School Sports Track Program?

Methodology

The study focused on the evaluation of the extent of implementation of the SHS Sports Track Program by DepEd–NCR using CIPP Evaluation Model. The program was evaluated using the model's four sections of Context, Input, Process, and Product. The study was conducted using the descriptive research design. It involves four sets of respondents with their different views or perspectives on the extent of the program. It aims to increase the level of knowledge of the program and strengthen the standpoint of various aspects. Data were analyzed and treated statistically.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the public schools in National Capital Region which offer Senior High School Sports Track Program to evaluate the program on the first three years of implementation.

Eight schools served as respondents, namely: University of Makati; Rizal Technological University, Mandaluyong; Muntinlupa National High School; Vito L. Belarmino—SHS (Jose P. Laurel, Sr. JHS), Quezon City; Sta. Elena High School, Marikina; Rizal High School; Fort Bonifacio High School, Makati; and Eulogio Rodriguez International School (ERIS), Mandaluyong.

Research Instrument

The K-12 curriculum and its implementation including the SHS Sports Track Program were anchored and mandated by RA 10533 as mentioned and discussed in the introduction and the setting of the study. Under this law, DepEd released orders and memoranda as guide in the implementation of the SHS including the Sports Track Program.

The following DepEd documents were used as standard basis for the research tool's development:

- 1) DepEd Order no. 43, s. 2013 Implementing Rules and Regulation of R.A 10533;
- 2) DepEd Order no. 3, s. 2016 The Hiring Guidelines of Senior High School Teachers;
- 3) DepEd Order no. 42, s. 2017 National Adaptation and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers;
- 4) DepEd Order no. 8, s. 2015 Policy and Guidelines in Classroom Assessment for the K-12 Basic Program;

- 5) DepEd Order no. 30, s. 2017 The Work Immersion Guidelines and Senior High School Curriculum guide in Practicum course;
- 6) DepED Order no. 51, s. 2015 The Guidelines of Implementation of Senior High School Program in Existing Public Junior High School and Integrated Schools, Establishment of Stand-Alone Public Senior High School and Conversion of Existing Public Elementary and JHSs Into Stand Alone SHSs;
- 7) DepEd Order no. 26, s. 2017 The Addendum of DepEd Order no. 51, s. 2015;
- 8) DepEd Order no. 25, s. 2015 Implementing Guidelines on The Special Program in Sports;
- 9) DepEd Order no. 10, s. 2015 Revised Guidelines on the Used of the Special Education Fund;
- 10) DepEd Order no. 42, s. 2015 Senior High School Career Guidance Program and Early Registration;
- 11) DepEd Order no. 13, s. 2012 Guidelines on the allocation Delivery and Distribution of (IM)Instructional Materials to Support The k-12 Curriculum;
- 12) DepEd Order no. 66, s. 2017 Implementing guidelines of off campus activities;
- 13) DepEd Memo no. 4, s. 2014 The Guidelines on the Preparation for the Implementation of the Senior High School (SHS) Program in Non- Dep Ed Schools for the School Year (SY) 2016-2017and onwards;
- 14) DepEd Memo no. 82, s. 2017 Learning Resources Management System Implementation in the Rationalized DepEd Structure; and
- 15) Sports Track Program's Curriculum Guides.

The study was guided by the CIPP framework as discussed in the theoretical framework. *Context evaluation* serves inputs to planning decisions to determine objectives. It is a kind of monitoring of the total system. *Input evaluation* provides information for determining how to utilize resources to meet program goals. *Process evaluation* provides periodic feedback to persons responsible for implementing plans and procedures and *Product evaluation's* purpose is to measure and to interpret attainments not only at the end of a program or project cycle but as often as necessary during the program. It serves the decision maker who must decide whether to continue, to terminate, or to modify a program.

This study is confined to the evaluation of the implementation of SHS Sports Track Program with respect to the program goals and objectives, in terms of internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (partner and linkages) and administrative support, extent of the implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies and implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum, work immersion program and seven (7) specialized courses.

There were four sets of questionnaires used to gather data: Senior High School Sports Track Program for the Grade 12 students (STIQS), Students who graduated from the program-Alumni (STIQS), SHS Sports Track faculty (STIQF) and for School Administrators (STIQA).

The four sets of questionnaires had almost the same content, however, the items were constructed based on respondent's integral part of the Sports Track Program. The questionnaire for the SHS Sports Track Program for the Grade 12 students/currently enrolled and for the alumni (STIQS) had the same content, however, there were items reflected for alumni respondents but were excluded for the Grade 12 questionnaire. This is so since there were items based from the learning competencies of the students which the Grade 12 have not taken up so far.

Data Gathering Procedure

In DepEd Schools, the researcher had a written request to the NCR Regional Director. Upon the approval of the Regional NCR office, the researcher requested the endorsement letter in every division to seek permission from the school's division offices in setting appointment to the specific school respondents to visit and administer the questionnaire.

In State Universities, the researcher also had a written request to the University Presidents. Upon the approval of the permission letter, the researcher proceeded to the assigned personnel/ school authorities to set an appointment to the target respondents.

For the alumni, the researcher traced the students who graduated from the program through the help of the Senior High School Sports Track Faculty and Sports Coordinator. For the University of Makati and Rizal Technological University, most of their alumni were enrolled in college in the same school. For the Sta. Elena High School, most of its alumni were enrolled in Philippine Normal University since they had a school partnership agreement. Some of the alumni of Fort Bonifacio High School proceeded also to the University of Makati. For this reason, the researcher had a chance to distribute the survey to the respondents.

The rest of the alumni were enrolled in different Universities and Colleges and some of them did not enter college, according to their Senior High School Sports Track Faculty and Sports Coordinator. In this case the researcher used online survey through the use of google docs/applications to reach the other alumni. The questionnaire for the Sports Track Program was put in the online questions through a survey link. The researcher shared the survey link to the sports coordinator who then sent it through email or in the closed group chat of the alumni to answer the survey.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The result of the survey was tabulated and treated statistically, the informal interview and Senior High School Sports Track Program documents were supplemented to the data analysis.

The following statistical tools were used in the treatment of data:

Weighted mean was used to determine the following:

- ✓ Extent of implementation of the program goals and objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program;
- ✓ Extent of implementation of the Program Plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (Partner and Linkages) and administrative support;
- ✓ Extent of implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies; and
- ✓ Extent of implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum, work immersion program and seven (7) specialized courses.

Results and Discussions

This chapter contains reported data collected around the four research questions. The discussion of the results and their interpretation is made according to the problems of the study. The data were presented in terms of the four thematic areas of the CIPP model which formulate the framework of the research design and discussed and analyzed according to the groups of respondents composed of the Sports Track Program alumni, administrators, faculty and currently enrolled students. The four research questions used for this evaluation were:

Context: Extent of implementation of the program goals and objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program.

Input: Extent of implementation of the Program Plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (Partner and Linkages) and administrative support.

Process: Extent of implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support competencies and learning.

Product: Extent of implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum, work immersion program and seven (7) specialized courses.

Description of Respondents

The respondents of the study were the public schools in National Capital Region which offer Senior High School Sports Track Program to evaluate the program on the first three years of implementation.

Eight schools served as respondents, namely: University of Makati; Rizal Technological University, Mandaluyong; Muntinlupa National High School; Vito L. Belarmino—SHS (Jose P. Laurel, Sr. JHS), Quezon City; Sta. Elena High School, Marikina; Rizal High School; Fort Bonifacio High School, Makati; and Eulogio Rodriguez International School (ERIS), Mandaluyong.

Table 1. Profile of Respondents According to Division, Number of Administrators, Faculty, Current Grade 12 Students and Alumni

School Respondents	Division	Sports Track Administrator	Faculty	Grade 12 Students	Alumni	Total
1 University of Makati	Makati	1	4	61	31	97
2 Rizal Technological University	Mandaluyong	1	2	19	16	38
3 Muntinlupa National High School	Muntinlupa	1	2	18	None	21
4 Vito L. Belarmino—SHS (Jose P. Laurel, Sr. JHS)	Quezon City	1	2	15	6	24
5 Sta. Elena High School	Marikina	1	2	29	11	43
6 Rizal High School	Pasig	1	2	29	9	41
7 Fort Bonifacio High School	Makati	1	2	31	20	54
8 Eulogio Rodrigez International School (ERIS)	Mandaluyong	1	2	5	5	13
	Total	8	18	207	98	331

Table 2. Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Actual Respondents

Groups	Number	Percentage
Sports Track Program Administrator	8	2.42%
Faculty	18	5.44%
Currently Enrolled Grade 12 Students	207	62.54%
Alumni	98	29.6%
Total	331	100%

As shown in Table 2, a total of 331 respondents were divided into different groups. There were eight Sports Track Program Administrators with a ratio of 2.42% from the total respondents. Eighteen (18) faculty members teaching specialized subjects in the program 5.44%. The Grade 12 currently enrolled students who actively participated in the survey comprise 62.54% or 207 out of 331 respondents and 98 alumni 29.6%.

Table 3. Alumni Responses on the Implementation of the Program Goals and Objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program

Context Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
	Frequency						
Program Goals and Objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program							
1. The program developed the learner’s sports competencies and skills and work ethics and values necessary for employment.	49	40	7	0	2	4.37	Great Extent
2. The program provided relevant content that made the learners competitive in the field of work	38	50	8	0	2	4.24	Great Extent
3. The program reinforced the learner’s interest to career opportunities	42	40	12	2	2	4.20	Great Extent
4. The program is designed for the learners in pursuing sports-related career, athlete development, fitness training, coaching and officiating	55	30	10	0	3	4.37	Great Extent
5. The program is designed for the learners to understand the basic principles and techniques in relation to physical education and recreation	51	36	8	0	3	4.35	Great Extent
6. The program discuss various factors that affect social, psychological, and cognitive development in sports leadership and management	41	38	15	0	4	4.14	High Extent
7. The program ensured the learners to have the life skills and competencies in safety, injury prevention and management in various sports and exercise settings for prompt and proper response during emergencies.	56	29	7	3	3	4.35	Great Extent
8. The program designed to facilitate lifelong learning for the learners	37	47	7	4	3	4.13	High Extent
9. The program empowered the learners to be competent and be harmonize in local and global communities	28	53	12	3	2	4.04	High Extent
Context Evaluation General Weighted Mean by the alumni respondents:						4.24	Great Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

Table 3 presents the alumni responses on the implementation of the program goals and objectives of the senior high school sports track program. It can be gleaned from the table that of the statements is in “Great Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.37, 4.24, 4.20, 4.37, 4.35, and 4.35 respectively. On the other hand, 3 statements namely: “The program discuss various factors that affect social, psychological, and cognitive development in sports leadership and management,” “The program designed to facilitate lifelong learning for the learners,” and “The program empowered the learners to be competent and be harmonize in local and global communities” were interpreted to have a “High Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.14, 4.13, and 4.04 respectively.

Table 4. Administrator’s Responses on the Implementation of the Program Goals and Objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program

Context Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
	Frequency						
Program Goals and Objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program							
1.The program developed the learner’s sports competencies and skills and work ethics and values necessary for employment.	5	3	0	0	0	4.63	Great Extent
2. The program provided relevant content that made the learners competitive in the field of work	5	2	1	0	0	4.50	Great Extent
3. The program reinforced the learner’s interest to career opportunities	4	4	0	0	0	4.50	Great Extent
4. The program is designed for the learners in pursuing sports-related career, athlete development, fitness training, coaching and officiating	7	1	0	0	0	4.88	Great Extent
5. The program is designed for the learners to understand the basic principles and techniques in relation to physical education and recreation	5	3	0	0	0	4.63	Great Extent
6. The program discuss various factors that affect social, psychological, and cognitive development in sports leadership and management	5	3	0	0	0	4.63	Great Extent
7.The program ensured the learners to have the life skills and competencies in safety, injury prevention and management in various sports and exercise settings for prompt and proper response during emergencies.	5	3	0	0	0	4.63	Great Extent
8. The program designed to facilitate lifelong learning for the learners	4	4	0	0	0	4.50	Great Extent
9.The program empowered the learners to be competent and be harmonize in local and global communities	4	2	2	0	0	4.25	Great Extent
Context General Weighted Mean by the Administrator Respondents:						4.57	Great Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

Table 4 presents the administrator’s responses on the implementation of the program goals and objectives of the senior high school sports track program.

In general, the overall weighted mean of 4.57 indicates that the implementation of the program goals and objectives of the senior high school sports track program has a “Great Extent” level of implementation as assessed by the administrator respondents.

The administrators had positive attitude towards the goals and objectives of the senior high school sports track program.

Table 5. Faculty Responses on the Implementation of the Program Goals and Objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program

Context Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
	Frequency						
Program Goals and Objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program							
1.The program developed the learner’s sports competencies and skills and work ethics and values necessary for employment.	11	6	1	0	0	4.56	Great Extent
2.The program provided relevant content that made the learners competitive in the field of work	9	8	1	0	0	4.44	Great Extent
3. The program reinforced the learner’s interest to career opportunities	2	16	0	0	0	4.11	High Extent
4.The program is designed for the learners in pursuing sports-related career, athlete development, fitness training, coaching and officiating	11	7	0	0	0	4.61	Great Extent
5. The program is designed for the learners to understand the basic principles and techniques in relation to physical education and recreation	8	10	0	0	0	4.44	Great Extent
6. The program discuss various factors that affect social, psychological, and cognitive development in sports leadership and management	7	9	2	0	0	4.28	Great Extent
7. The program ensured the learners to have the life skills and competencies in safety, injury prevention and management in various sports and exercise settings for prompt and proper response during emergencies.	11	7	0	0	0	4.61	Great Extent
8.The program designed to facilitate lifelong learning for the learners	8	8	2	0	0	4.33	Great Extent
9.The program empowered the learners to be competent and be harmonize in local and global communities	7	8	3	0	0	4.22	Great Extent
Context General Weighted Mean by the Faculty Respondents:						4.40	Great Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

Table 5 shows the faculty members’ responses on the implementation of the program goals and objectives of the senior high school sports track program. In general, the overall weighted mean of 4.40 indicates that the implementation of the program goals and objectives of the senior high school sports track program have a “Great Extent” level of implementation as assessed by the faculty respondents.

However, it can be gleaned from the table; “The program reinforced the learner’s interest to career opportunities” has the lowest emphasis.

Table 6. Currently Enrolled Student’s Responses on the Implementation of the Program Goals and Objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program

Context Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
	Frequency						
Program Goals and Objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program							
1. The program developed your sports competencies and skills and work ethics and values necessary for employment.	86	92	27	1	1	4.26	Great Extent
2. The program provided relevant content that made you competitive in the field of work	71	92	35	7	2	4.08	High Extent
3. The program reinforced your interest to career opportunities	79	68	55	3	2	4.06	High Extent
4. The program is designed for you in pursuing sports-related career, athlete development, fitness training, coaching and officiating	110	67	21	9	0	4.34	Great Extent
5. The program is designed for you to understand the basic principles and techniques in relation to physical education and recreation	100	65	35	4	3	4.23	Great Extent
6. The program discuss various factors that affect social, psychological, and cognitive development in sports leadership and management	95	83	28	1	0	4.31	Great Extent
7. The program ensured you to have the life skills and competencies in safety, injury prevention and management in various sports and exercise settings for prompt and proper response during emergencies.	111	77	16	1	2	4.42	Great Extent
8. The program designed to facilitate lifelong learning for you	88	79	31	9	0	4.19	High Extent
9. The program empowered you to be competent and be harmonize in local and global communities	62	84	51	6	4	3.94	High Extent
Context General Weighted Mean by Currently Enrolled Students:						4.20	Great Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

Table 6 presents the currently enrolled students’ responses on the implementation of the program goals and objectives of the senior high school sports track program. It can be gleaned from the table that five of the statements were interpreted to have a “Great Extent” level of implementation.

In general, the overall weighted mean of 4.20 indicates that the implementation of the program goals and objectives of the senior high school sports track program has a “Great Extent” level of implementation as assessed by the currently enrolled student respondents. However, there are currently enrolled students who interpreted statements in the extent of implementation of the goal

and objectives of the program were not implemented. It can be gleaned from the statements 2, 3, 8 and 9.

Table 7. Summary of Responses on the Implementation of the Program Goals and Objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program

Context Evaluation Statements	Alumni		Administrator		Faculty		Currently Enrolled Students		Overall Weighted Mean	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
Program Goals and Objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program										
1. The program developed the learner’s sports competencies and skills and work ethics and values necessary for employment.	4.37	GE	4.63	GE	4.56	GE	4.26	GE	4.46	GE
2. The program provided relevant content that made the learners competitive in the field of work	4.24	GE	4.50	GE	4.44	GE	4.08	HE	4.32	GE
3. The program reinforced the learner’s interest to career opportunities	4.20	GE	4.50	GE	4.11	HE	4.06	HE	4.22	GE
4. The program is designed for the learners in pursuing sports-related career, athlete development, fitness training, coaching and officiating	4.37	GE	4.88	GE	4.61	GE	4.34	GE	4.55	GE
5. The program is designed for the learners to understand the basic principles and techniques in relation to physical education and recreation	4.35	GE	4.63	GE	4.44	GE	4.23	GE	4.41	GE
6. The program discuss various factors that affect social, psychological, and cognitive development in sports leadership and management	4.14	HE	4.63	GE	4.28	GE	4.31	GE	4.34	GE
7. The program ensured the learners to have the life skills and competencies in safety, injury prevention and management in various sports and exercise settings for prompt and proper response during emergencies.	4.35	GE	4.63	GE	4.61	GE	4.42	GE	4.50	GE
8. The program designed to facilitate lifelong learning for the learners	4.13	HE	4.50	GE	4.33	GE	4.19	HE	4.29	GE
9. The program empowered the learners to be competent and be harmonize in local and global communities	4.04	HE	4.25	GE	4.22	GE	3.94	HE	4.11	HE
Context Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean:									4.35	GE
Legend: "Not Implemented" (NI) - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" (PE) - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" (ME)- (2.60-3.39), "High Extent"(HE) - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent"(GE) - (4.20-5.00).										

Table 7 displays the summary of responses of the 4 groups of respondents on the Implementation of the Program Goals and Objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program. The context evaluation statement namely: ‘The program developed the learner’s sports competencies and skills and work ethics and values necessary for employment’ was interpreted to have a “Great extent”

level implementation by all of the respondents. This statement obtained the weighted mean of 4.37, 4.63, 4.56, and 4.26 respectively. The overall weighted mean is interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. Statement namely: “The program provided relevant content that made the learners competitive in the field of work” was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation by the alumni, administrators, and faculty members. However, it was interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation by the currently enrolled students. These statements obtained the weighted means of 4.24, 4.50, 4.44, and 4.08 respectively. The overall weighted mean is interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. The statement obtained 4.32. The statement namely: “The program reinforced the learner’s interest to career opportunities” was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation by the alumni and administrators. However, it is interpreted “High Extent “level of implementation by the faculty and currently enrolled students. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.20, 4.50, 4.11, and 4.06 respectively. The overall weighted mean is interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. The statement obtained 4.22.

Table 8. Alumni’s Responses on the Implementation of the Program Plan in Internal and External Stakeholder Support, Societal Support (Partner and Linkages) and Administrative Support

Input Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
	Frequency						
Internal and External Stakeholder Support							
1.Faculty handling specialized course is licensed and sport practitioner	37	39	18	1	3	4.08	High Extent
2.The school is assisted by external partner like industry in every off- campus activities	37	36	19	3	3	4.03	High Extent
3.Parents participated in planning activity in off campus through PTA meeting	22	42	27	1	6	3.74	High Extent
4.The school has a strong partnership with the community and industry for its practicum and work immersion.	33	42	18	2	3	4.02	High Extent
5.Learner’s Resources are available in the school like books and module related the Sports Track Program	32	40	17	5	4	3.93	High Extent
6.Senior High School Faculty updated their sports knowledge and skills through in- service training	37	43	13	2	3	4.11	High Extent
7.The school provided adequate facilities and equipment	25	51	15	3	4	3.92	High Extent
8.Necessary equipment for the development of skills are readily available	30	45	15	5	3	3.96	High Extent
General Weighted Mean of Internal and External Support by the Alumni Respondents:						3.97	High Extent
Societal Support							
1.The selected partner industry and community has a strong program for sports and skills development	31	50	10	4	3	4.04	High Extent
2.The company/ institution partner of the school is aligned in the sports track program. (Fitness Shops, Gym, Sorts Club)	32	40	20	2	4	3.96	High Extent
3.Your school enter partnership in sports track in Fitness Ships, Gym and Sports Club	39	29	22	3	5	3.96	High Extent
4.School and Industry collaboration is strong which ensure the meaningful practicum	30	44	19	3	2	3.99	High Extent
General Weighted Mean of Societal Support by Alumni Respondents:						3.98	High Extent

Administrative Support							
1.The school is compliant with Dep Ed’s requirements for budget allocation to ensure quality program implementation	24	47	18	4	5	3.83	High Extent
2.During immersion the school avail insurance for the learners	26	43	22	3	4	3.86	High Extent
3.The school and the school leaders conduct in-service training on content pedagogy and performance standard of K-12 curriculum	29	49	16	2	2	4.03	High Extent
4.The school is supporting the intramurals and sports fest activities	47	32	12	4	3	4.18	High Extent
General Weighted Mean of Administrative Support by the Alumni Respondents:						3.97	High Extent
Input Evaluation Grand Weighted by Alumni Respondents:						3.98	High Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

Table 8 shows the responses of the alumni respondents on the implementation of the program plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (partner and linkages) and administrative support. It can be gleaned from the table that all of the statements were interpreted to have a “High Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.08, 4.03, 3.74, 4.02, 3.93, 4.11, 3.92, 3.96, 4.04, 3.96, 3.96, 3.99, 3.83, 3.86, 4.03, and 4.18 respectively.

The result indicates that the implementation of the program plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (partner and linkages) and administrative support was highly implemented.

Table 9. Administrator’s Responses on the Implementation of the Program Plan in Internal and External Stakeholder Support, Societal Support (Partner and Linkages) and Administrative Support

Input Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
	Frequency						
Internal and External Stakeholder Support							
1.Faculty handling specialized course is licensed and sport practitioner	4	4	0	0	0	4.50	Great Extent
2.The school is assisted by external partner like industry in every off- campus activities	3	2	3	0	0	4.00	High Extent
3.Parents participated in planning activity in off campus through PTA meeting	2	3	3	0	0	3.88	High Extent
4.The school has a strong partnership with the community and industry for its practicum and work immersion.	3	3	2	0	0	4.13	High Extent
5.Learner’s Resources are available in the school like books and module related the Sports Track Program	0	5	2	1	0	3.50	High Extent
6.Senior High School Faculty updated their sports knowledge and skills through in- service training	3	4	1	0	0	4.25	Great Extent
7.The school provided adequate facilities and equipment	2	3	3	0	0	3.88	High Extent
8.Necessary equipment for the development of skills are readily available	2	3	3	0	0	3.88	High Extent
General Weighted Mean of Internal and External Support by the Administrator Respondents:						4.00	High Extent
Societal Support							

1. The selected partner industry and community has a strong program for sports and skills development	2	5	1	0	0	4.13	High Extent
2. The company/ institution partner of the school is aligned in the sports track program. (Fitness Shops, Gym, Sports Club)	5	1	2	0	0	4.38	Great Extent
3. Your school enter partnership in sports track in Fitness Shops, Gym and Sports Club	3	4	1	0	0	4.25	Great Extent
4. School and Industry collaboration is strong which ensure the meaningful practicum	2	6	0	0	0	4.25	Great Extent
General Weighted Mean of the Societal Support by the Administrator Respondents:						4.25	Great Extent
Administrative Support							
1. The school is compliant with Dep Ed's requirements for budget allocation to ensure quality program implementation	3	3	2	0	0	4.13	High Extent
2. During immersion the school avail insurance for the learners	2	5	1	0	0	4.13	High Extent
3. The school and the school leaders conduct in- service training on content pedagogy and performance standard of K-12 curriculum	5	3	0	0	0	4.63	Great Extent
4. The school is supporting the intramurals and sports fest activities	8	0	0	0	0	5.00	Great Extent
General Weighted Mean of the Administrative Support by the Administrator Respondents:						4.47	Great Extent
Input Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean by the Administrator:						4.24	Great Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

Table 9 reveals the responses of the administrator respondents on the implementation of the program plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (partner and linkages) and administrative support. The result indicates that the implementation of the program plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (partner and linkages) and administrative support were greatly implemented.

Table 10. Faculty Responses on the Implementation of the Program Plan in Internal and External Stakeholder Support, Societal Support (Partner and Linkages) and Administrative Support

Input Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
	Frequency						
Internal and External Stakeholder Support							
1. Faculty handling specialized course is licensed and sport practitioner	9	8	0	1	0	4.39	Great Extent
2. The school is assisted by external partner like industry in every off- campus activities	5	7	6	0	0	3.94	High Extent
3. Parents participated in planning activity in off campus through PTA meeting	3	6	9	0	0	3.67	High Extent
4. The school has a strong partnership with the community and industry for its practicum and work immersion.	5	10	3	0	0	4.11	High Extent
5. Learner's Resources are available in the school like books and module related the Sports Track Program	1	7	10	0	0	3.50	High Extent

6.Senior High School Faculty updated their sports knowledge and skills through in- service training	5	12	1	0	0	4.22	Great Extent
7.The school provided adequate facilities and equipment	4	13	1	0	0	4.17	High Extent
8.Necessary equipment for the development of skills are readily available	4	12	2	0	0	4.11	High Extent
General Weighted Mean of Internal and External Support by the Faculty Respondents:						4.03	High Extent
Societal Support							
1.The selected partner industry and community has a strong program for sports and skills development	5	12	0	0	1	4.11	High Extent
2.The company/ institution partner of the school is aligned in the sports track program. (Fitness Shops, Gym, Sorts Club)	6	11	0	0	1	4.17	High Extent
3.Your school enter partnership in sports track in Fitness Ships, Gym and Sports Club	3	14	0	0	1	4.00	High Extent
4.School and Industry collaboration is strong which ensure the meaningful practicum	10	7	0	1	0	4.44	Great Extent
General Weighted Mean of Societal Support by the Faculty Respondents:						4.18	High Extent
Administrative Support							
1.The school is compliant with Dep Ed’s requirements for budget allocation to ensure quality program implementation	9	8	1	0	0	4.44	Great Extent
2.During immersion the school avail insurance for the learners	5	12	0	1	0	4.17	High Extent
3.The school and the school leaders conduct in- service training on content pedagogy and performance standard of K-12 curriculum	5	11	2	0	0	4.17	High Extent
4.The school is supporting the intramurals and sports fest activities	9	8	0	0	1	4.33	Great Extent
General Weighted Mean of Administrative Support by the Faculty Respondents:						4.28	Great Extent
Input Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean by the Faculty Respondents:						4.16	High Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

Table 10 shows the responses of the faculty members on the implementation of the program plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (partner and linkages) and administrative support.

In general, the overall weighted mean of the administrative support was interpreted to “Great Extent” level of implementation.

The statements obtained weighted mean of 4.28. However, the extent of internal and external stakeholder and societal approach were interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained weighted mean of 4.03 and 4.18 respectively.

The overall weighted mean in the input evaluation by the faculty was 4.16 and interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation.

The result indicates that the implementation of the program plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (partner and linkages) and administrative support were highly implemented.

Table 11. Currently Enrolled Student Responses on the Implementation of the Program Plan in Internal and External Stakeholder Support, Societal Support (Partner and Linkages) and Administrative Support

Input Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
	Frequency						
Internal and External Stakeholder Support							
1. Faculty handling specialized course is licensed and sport practitioner	73	80	39	13	2	4.01	High Extent
2. The school is assisted by external partner like industry in every off- campus activities	68	68	53	12	6	3.87	High Extent
3. Parents participated in planning activity in off campus through PTA meeting	55	48	78	15	11	3.58	High Extent
4. The school has a strong partnership with the community and industry for its practicum and work immersion.	85	74	34	12	2	4.10	High Extent
5. Learner’s Resources are available in the school like books and module related the Sports Track Program	49	80	51	18	9	3.69	High Extent
6. Senior High School Faculty updated their sports knowledge and skills through in- service training	89	71	31	11	5	4.10	High Extent
7. The school provided adequate facilities and equipment	63	83	41	16	4	3.89	High Extent
8. Necessary equipment for the development of skills are readily available	55	84	48	16	4	3.82	High Extent
General Weighted Mean of Internal and External Support by the Currently Enrolled Students:						3.88	High Extent
Societal Support							
1. The selected partner industry and community has a strong program for sports and skills development	70	92	34	9	2	4.06	High Extent
2. The company/ institution partner of the school is aligned in the sports track program. (Fitness Shops, Gym, Sorts Club)	84	60	49	11	3	4.02	High Extent
3. Your school enter partnership in sports track in Fitness Ships, Gym and Sports Club	72	67	42	19	7	3.86	High Extent
4. School and Industry collaboration is strong which ensure the meaningful practicum	62	87	40	11	7	3.90	High Extent
General Weighted Mean of Societal Support by the Currently Enrolled Students:						3.96	High Extent
Administrative Support							
1. The school is compliant with Dep Ed’s requirements for budget allocation to ensure quality program implementation	67	72	47	18	3	3.88	High Extent
2. During immersion the school avail insurance for you	62	64	53	15	13	3.71	High Extent
3. The school and the school leaders conduct in- service training on content pedagogy and performance standard of K-12 curriculum	79	75	41	10	2	4.06	High Extent
4. The school is supporting the intramurals and sports fest activities	103	70	23	7	4	4.26	Great Extent
General Weighted Mean of Administrative Support by the Currently Enrolled Students:						3.98	High Extent
Input Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean by the Currently Enrolled Students:						3.94	High Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

Table 11 shows the responses of the currently enrolled student respondents on the implementation of the program plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (partner and linkages) and administrative support.

The result indicates that the implementation of the program plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (partner and linkages) and administrative support were highly implemented based on the currently enrolled student’s evaluation.

Table 12. Summary of Responses on the Implementation of the Program Plan in Internal and External Stakeholder Support, Societal Support (Partner and Linkages) and Administrative Support

Input Evaluation Statements	Alumni		Administrator		Faculty		Currently Enrolled Students		General Weighted Mean	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
Internal and External Support										
1. Faculty handling specialized course is licensed and sport practitioner	4.08	HE	4.50	GE	4.39	GE	4.01	HE	4.25	GE
2. The school is assisted by external partner like industry in every off- campus activities	4.03	HE	4.00	HE	3.94	HE	3.87	HE	3.96	HE
3. Parents participated in planning activity in off campus through PTA meeting	3.74	HE	3.88	HE	3.67	HE	3.58	HE	3.72	HE
4. The school has a strong partnership with the community and industry for its practicum and work immersion.	4.02	HE	4.13	HE	4.11	HE	4.10	HE	4.09	HE
5. Learner’s Resources are available in the school like books and module related the Sports Track Program	3.93	HE	3.50	HE	3.50	HE	3.69	HE	3.66	HE
6. Senior High School Faculty updated their sports knowledge and skills through in- service training	4.11	HE	4.2 5	GE	4.22	GE	4.10	HE	4.17	HE
7. The school provided adequate facilities and equipment	3.92	HE	3.88	HE	4.17	HE	3.89	HE	3.97	HE
8. Necessary equipment for the development of skills are readily available	3.96	HE	3.88	HE	4.11	HE	3.82	HE	3.94	HE
Internal and External Support General Weighted Mean by all of the Respondents:									3.97	HE
Societal Support										
1. The selected partner industry and community has a strong program for sports and skills development	4.04	HE	4.13	HE	4.11	HE	4.06	HE	4.09	HE
2. The company/ institution partner of the school is aligned in the sports track program. (Fitness Shops, Gym, Sorts Club)	3.96	HE	4.38	GE	4.17	HE	4.02	HE	4.13	HE
3. Your school enter partnership in sports track in Fitness Ships, Gym and Sports Club	3.96	HE	4.25	GE	4.00	HE	3.86	HE	4.02	HE
4. School and Industry	3.99	HE	4.25	GE	4.44	GE	3.90	HE	4.15	HE

collaboration is strong which ensure the meaningful practicum										
Societal Support General Weighted Mean by all of the Respondents:									4.09	HE
Administrative Support										
1.The school is compliant with Dep Ed’s requirements for budget allocation to ensure quality program implementation	3.83	HE	4.13	HE	4.44	GE	3.88	HE	4.1	HE
2.During immersion the school avail insurance for the learners	3.86	HE	4.13	HE	4.17	HE	3.71	HE	4.00	HE
3.The school and the school leaders conduct in- service training on content pedagogy and performance standard of K-12 curriculum	4.03	HE	4.63	GE	4.17	HE	4.06	HE	4.20	GE
4.The school is supporting the intramurals and sports fest activities	4.18	HE	5.00	GE	4.33	GE	4.26	GE	4.4	GE
Administrative Support General Weighted Mean by all of the Respondents:									4.17	HE
Input Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean									4.07	HE
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).										

Table 12 displays the summary of responses of the 4 groups of respondents on the Implementation of the Program Plan in Internal and External Stakeholder Support, Societal Support (Partner and Linkages) and Administrative Support.

The input evaluation statement namely: “Faculty handling specialized course is licensed and sport practitioner” was interpreted to have “Great Extent” by the administrators and faculty. The overall weighted mean of the statement is 4.25 and interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation.

The input evaluation is to assess the competing strategies, work plans and budgets of the program for identifying the strategies which best meet the identified objectives and goals and to maximize the available resources and design.

In general, the overall weighted mean of the administrative support, internal and external stakeholder and societal approach were interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation. These obtained weighted mean of 3.97, 4.09 and 4.17 respectively. The overall weighted mean in the input evaluation by the faculty was 4.07 and interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation. The result indicates that the implementation of the program plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (partner and linkages) and administrative support were highly implemented. However, it implies to continue improving the implementation of administrative support, internal and external stakeholder and societal approach.

However, in Internal and External Stakeholder Support, it can be gleaned from the table that the statement namely; “Parents participated in planning activity in off campus through PTA meeting”, “Learner’s Resources are available in the school like books and module related the Sports Track Program” and “Necessary equipment for the development of skills are readily available” had the lowest emphasis.

In Societal Support, it can be gleaned from the table that the statement namely; “The selected partner industry and community has a strong program for sports and skills development”, “The company/ institution partner of the school is aligned in the sports track program” and “School and Industry collaboration is strong which ensure the meaningful practicum” had the lowest emphasis. In

Administrative Support, it can be gleaned from the table that statements namely; “The school is compliant with Dep Ed’s requirements for budget allocation to ensure quality program implementation”, “During immersion the school avail insurance for the learners” and “The school is supporting the intramurals and sports fest activities” had the lowest emphasis. It can be observed that among the domains, the same with the other respondent’s assessment, the Internal and External Stakeholder Support had the lowest emphasis.

Process: Extent of Implementation of Seven (7) specialized Courses in terms of Curricula Support System, Instructional Support and Learning Competencies

Table 13 on the next page shows the alumni responses on the implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies.

Table 13. Alumni Responses on the Implementation of Seven (7) specialized Courses in terms of Curricula Support System, Instructional Support and Learning Competencies

Process Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
	Frequency						
Curricula Support System							
1.The SHS faculty applied a range of appropriate strategies that maintain learning environment that motivate learning to for productively	36	35	24	1	2	4.04	High Extent
2. Your SHS faculty demonstrated knowledge and understanding of differentiated teaching to suit the learner’s gender, needs and interest	38	48	9	1	2	4.21	Great Extent
3.The SHS faculty applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	38	42	16	0	2	4.16	High Extent
4.The SHS faculty planned managed and implemented developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	36	43	14	2	3	4.09	High Extent
5.The SHS faculty managed the learner’s behavior constructively by applying positive and nonviolent discipline	36	44	15	1	2	4.13	High Extent
Curricula Support System General Weighted Mean by the Alumni:						4.13	High Extent
Instructional Support							
1. The school has adequate facilities, equipment in sports	32	39	19	6	2	3.95	High Extent
2. The instructional materials and teacher’s manual were always available and provides modules for you for out of school approach	19	54	20	3	2	3.87	High Extent
3. The SHS faculty designed, selected, organized and used diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	32	43	19	2	2	4.03	High Extent
4. The SHS faculty monitored and evaluated learner progress and achievement using learner appropriate	29	42	22	5	0	3.97	High Extent

assessment tools.							
5. The SHS faculty communicated promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians.	27	50	15	5	1	3.99	High Extent
6. The SHS faculty provided timely and accurate feedback	36	44	15	1	2	4.13	High Extent
7. The teacher utilized assessment data to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices	38	41	16	3	0	4.16	High Extent
Instructional Support General Weighted Mean by the Alumni:						4.01	High Extent
Learning Competencies							
1. The learner's knowledge and skills in Safety and First Aid are applied in real life situation	50	36	8	3	1	4.34	Great Extent
2. The learners observed safety awareness to prevent untoward incident	36	49	9	3	1	4.18	High Extent
3. The learners can discuss confidently the nature, purpose, procedure of movement screen for efficient and effective performance in different theories of motion	38	42	14	1	3	4.13	High Extent
4. The learners can explain clearly the fundamental concepts and principles, proper communication techniques of coaching in relation to ethical standard and strategies in monitoring performance	28	48	18	1	3	3.99	High Extent
5. The learners can identify surely how motivation, value of effective communication and group cohesion, arousal and anxiety affect sports performance and exercise participation	31	39	18	8	2	3.91	High Extent
6. The learners can distinguish truly the importance of test result as means of set fitness and can adjust training parameters according to training response	35	44	13	6	0	4.10	High Extent
7. The learners can determine immediately the fundamental concept, principle, skills and mechanics of sports officiating, activity management and elements of an event plans	28	52	13	3	2	4.03	High Extent
8. The learners can demonstrate affectively the quality of leadership, safe and effective sports exercise, value and professional ethics in the conduct of fitness and recreation activities	36	43	15	1	3	4.10	High Extent
Learning Competencies General Weighted Mean by the Alumni:						4.10	High Extent
Process Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean by the Alumni:						4.08	High Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

In general, the overall weighted mean of the curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies were interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained weighted mean of 4.13, 4.01 and 4.10 respectively.

The overall weighted mean in the input evaluation by the faculty was 4.08 and interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation.

Table 14 below shows that the administrator responses on the implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system and instructional support.

Table 14. Administrator Responses on the Implementation of Seven (7) specialized Courses in terms of Curricula Support System and Instructional Support

Process Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
Frequency							
Curricula Support System							
1. The SHS faculty applied a range of appropriate strategies that maintain learning environment that motivate learning to for productively	4	4	0	0	0	4.50	Great Extent
2. Your SHS faculty demonstrated knowledge and understanding of differentiated teaching to suit the learner’s gender, needs and interest	5	3	0	0	0	4.63	Great Extent
3. The SHS faculty applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	3	5	0	0	0	4.38	Great Extent
4. The SHS faculty planned managed and implemented developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	5	3	0	0	0	4.63	Great Extent
5. The SHS faculty managed the learner’s behavior constructively by applying positive and nonviolent discipline	4	4	0	0	0	4.50	Great Extent
Curricula Support System General Weighted Mean by the Administrator:						4.53	Great Extent
Instructional Support							
1. The school has adequate facilities, equipment in sports	1	5	2	0	0	3.88	High Extent
2. The instructional materials and teacher’s manual were always available and provides modules for you for out of school approach	2	3	3	0	0	3.88	High Extent
3. The SHS faculty designed, selected, organized and used diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	3	5	0	0	0	4.38	Great Extent
4. The SHS faculty monitored and evaluated learner progress and achievement using learner appropriate assessment tools.	2	6	0	0	0	4.25	Great Extent
5. The SHS faculty communicated promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians.	3	5	0	0	0	4.38	Great Extent
6. The SHS faculty provided timely and accurate feedback	2	6	0	0	0	4.25	Great Extent
7. The teacher utilized assessment date to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices	1	6	1	0	0	4.00	High Extent
Instructional Support General Weighted Mean by the Administrator:						4.15	High Extent
Process Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean by the Administrator:						4.34	Great Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

In general, the overall weighted mean of the curricula support and instructional support obtained a weighted mean of 4.53 and was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. However, instructional support obtained 4.15 weighted mean and was interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation. The overall weighted mean in the input evaluation by the faculty was 4.015 and interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation. The result indicates that

the implementation of extent of curricula support system and instructional system was highly implemented based on the alumni's evaluation. The administrator respondents had a positive attitude on the extent of implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system and instructional support.

Table 15. Faculty Responses on the Implementation of Seven (7) specialized Courses in terms of Curricula Support System, Instructional Support and Learning Competencies

Process Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
	Frequency						
Curricula Support							
1. The SHS faculty applied a range of appropriate strategies that maintain learning environment that motivate learning to for productively	9	8	0	1	0	4.39	Great Extent
2. Your SHS faculty demonstrated knowledge and understanding of differentiated teaching to suit the learner's gender, needs and interest	8	9	0	0	1	4.28	Great Extent
3. The SHS faculty applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	7	10	0	1	0	4.28	Great Extent
4. The SHS faculty planned managed and implemented developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	8	9	0	1	0	4.33	Great Extent
5. The SHS faculty managed the learner's behavior constructively by applying positive and nonviolent discipline	8	9	1	0	0	4.39	Great Extent
Curricula Support General Weighted Mean by the Faculty Respondents:						4.33	Great Extent
Instructional Support							
1. The school has adequate facilities, equipment in sports	4	13	1	0	0	4.17	High Extent
2. The instructional materials and teacher's manual were always available and provides modules for you for out of school approach	5	7	5	0	1	3.83	High Extent
3. The SHS faculty designed, selected, organized and used diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	6	11	0	1	0	4.22	Great Extent
4. The SHS faculty monitored and evaluated learner progress and achievement using learner appropriate assessment tools.	7	10	1	0	0	4.33	Great Extent
5. The SHS faculty communicated promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians.	5	5	7	0	1	3.72	High Extent
6. The SHS faculty provided timely and accurate feedback	7	10	0	1	0	4.28	Great Extent
7. The teacher utilized assessment date to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices	6	11	1	0	0	4.28	Great Extent
Instructional Support General Weighted Mean by the Faculty Responds:						4.12	High Extent
Learning Competencies							
1. The learner's knowledge and skills in Safety and First Aid are applied in real life situation	9	8	0	1	0	4.39	Great Extent

2. The learners observed safety awareness to prevent untoward incident	7	10	0	1	0	4.28	Great Extent
3. The learners can discuss confidently the nature, purpose, procedure of movement screen for efficient and effective performance in different theories of motion	10	7	0	1	0	4.44	Great Extent
4. The learners can explain clearly the fundamental concepts and principles, proper communication techniques of coaching in relation to ethical standard and strategies in monitoring performance	9	8	1	0	0	4.44	Great Extent
5. The learners can identify surely how motivation, value of effective communication and group cohesion, arousal and anxiety affect sports performance and exercise participation	10	6	2	0	0	4.44	Great Extent
6. The learners can distinguish truly the importance of test result as means of set fitness and can adjust training parameters according to training response	6	11	1	0	0	4.28	Great Extent
7. The learners can determine immediately the fundamental concept, principle, skills and mechanics of sports officiating, activity management and elements of an event plans	4	13	0	0	1	4.06	High Extent
8. The learners can demonstrate affectively the quality of leadership, safe and effective sports exercise, value and professional ethics in the conduct of fitness and recreation activities	5	12	0	0	1	4.11	High Extent
Learning Competencies General Weighted Mean by the Faculty Respondents:						4.31	Great Extent
Process Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean by the Faculty Respondents:						4.25	Great Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

Table 15 reveals faculty responses on the implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies.

In general, the overall weighted mean of the curricula support and learning competencies obtained a weighted mean of 4.33 and 4.31 respectively. It was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. However, instructional support obtained 4.12 weighted mean and was interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation.

The overall weighted mean in the input evaluation by the faculty was 4.25 and interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. The result indicates that the implementation of extent of curricula support system and instructional system were highly implemented as evaluated by faculty members.

Table 16 below reveals the currently enrolled students’ responses on the implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies. It can be gleaned from the table that statements “The SHS faculty applied a range of appropriate strategies that maintain learning environment that motivate learning to for productively”, “Your SHS faculty demonstrated knowledge and understanding of differentiated teaching to suit the learners gender, needs and interest”, “The SHS faculty applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas”, “The SHS faculty planned managed and implemented developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts”, “The SHS faculty managed the learners behavior constructively by applying positive and nonviolent discipline”.

Table 16. Currently Enrolled Students Responses on the Implementation of Seven (7) specialized Courses in terms of Curricula Support System, Instructional Support and Learning Competencies

Process Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
	Frequency						
Curricula Support System							
1.The SHS faculty applied a range of appropriate strategies that maintain learning environment that motivate learning to for productively	65	81	49	9	3	3.95	High Extent
2.Your SHS faculty demonstrated knowledge and understanding of differentiated teaching to suit the learner’s gender, needs and interest	76	73	42	14	2	4.00	High Extent
3.The SHS faculty applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	66	93	37	8	3	4.02	High Extent
4.The SHS faculty planned managed and implemented developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	71	80	47	6	3	4.01	High Extent
5.The SHS faculty managed the learner’s behavior constructively by applying positive and nonviolent discipline	67	85	42	9	4	3.98	High Extent
Curricula Support System Overall Weighted Mean:						3.99	High Extent
Instructional Support							
1.The school has adequate facilities, equipment in sports	45	90	48	19	5	3.73	High Extent
2.The instructional materials and teacher’s manual were always available and provides modules for you for out of school approach	80	70	41	10	6	4.00	High Extent
3.The SHS faculty designed, selected, organized and used diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	84	83	28	10	2	4.14	High Extent
4.The SHS faculty monitored and evaluated learner progress and achievement using learner appropriate assessment tools.	66	103	30	3	5	4.07	High Extent
5.The SHS faculty communicated promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians.	81	60	52	12	2	4.00	High Extent
6.The SHS faculty provided timely and accurate feedback	60	79	45	19	4	3.83	High Extent
7.The teacher utilized assessment date to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices	75	90	34	5	3	4.11	High Extent
Instructional Support General Weighted Mean by the Currently Enrolled Students:						3.98	High Extent
Learning Competencies							
1.Your knowledge and skills in Safety and First Aid are applied in real life situation	101	83	14	6	3	4.32	Great Extent
2.You observed safety awareness to prevent untoward incident	106	66	25	9	1	4.29	Great Extent

3.You can discuss confidently the nature, purpose, procedure of movement screen for efficient and effective performance in different theories of motion	79	77	45	5	1	4.10	High Extent
4.You can explain clearly the fundamental concepts and principles, proper communication techniques of coaching in relation to ethical standard and strategies in monitoring performance	78	84	40	5	0	4.14	High Extent
5.You can identify surely how motivation, value of effective communication and group cohesion, arousal and anxiety affect sports performance and exercise participation	93	86	24	3	1	4.29	Great Extent
Learning Competencies General Weighted Mean by Currently Enrolled Students:						4.23	Great Extent
Process Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean by Currently Enrolled Students:						4.07	High Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

The overall weighted mean of the learning competencies was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. The statement obtained weighted mean of 4.23. However, the curricula support and instructional support were interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained weighted mean of 3.99 and 3.98 respectfully.

In general, the overall weighted mean of 4.07 indicates that the assessment of the currently enrolled respondents on the implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies have a “Great Extent” level of implementation.

However, all of the statements on the extent of the implementation of (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies were interpreted by some of the currently enrolled student as “not implemented”.

Table 17 below displays the summary of the responses of the 4 groups of respondents on the Implementation of Seven (7) specialized Courses in terms of Curricula Support System, Instructional Support and Learning Competencies.

The process evaluation statement namely, “The SHS faculty applied a range of appropriate strategies that maintain learning environment that motivate learning to for productively” was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation by the admin and faculty. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.5 and 4.39 respectively. However, it was interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation by the alumni and currently enrolled students. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.04 and 3.95 respectively.

The overall weighted mean of the scale item is interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation as it obtained 4.22 weighted mean. The result shows that the application of range of strategies in maintaining learning environment in motivating learning was greatly applied in the Senior High School Sports Track Program. The statement namely; “Your SHS faculty demonstrated knowledge and understanding of differentiated teaching to suit the learner’s gender, needs and interest” was interpreted to have a “Great Extent” by alumni, faculty and admin. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4. 21, 4.63 and 4.28 respectively However, it was interpreted “High Extent” by currently enrolled students. The statement obtained 4.00 weighted mean. The overall mean obtained 4.28 and interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation.

Table 17. Summary of Responses on the Implementation Seven (7 Students) specialized Courses in terms of Curricula Support System, Instructional Support and Learning Competencies

Process Evaluation Statements	Alumni		Administrator		Faculty		Currently Enrolled Students		Overall Weighted Mean	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
Curricula Support System										
1. The SHS faculty applied a range of appropriate strategies that maintain learning environment that motivate learning to for productively	4.04	HE	4.50	GE	4.39	GE	3.95	HE	4.22	GE
2. The SHS faculty demonstrated knowledge and understanding of differentiated teaching to suit the learner's gender, needs and interest	4.21	GE	4.63	GE	4.28	GE	4.00	HE	4.28	GE
3. The SHS faculty applied knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	4.16	HE	4.38	GE	4.28	GE	4.02	HE	4.21	GE
4. The SHS faculty planned managed and implemented developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	4.09	HE	4.63	GE	4.33	GE	4.01	HE	4.26	GE
5. The SHS faculty managed the learner's behavior constructively by applying positive and nonviolent discipline	4.13	HE	4.50	GE	4.39	GE	3.98	HE	4.25	GE
Curricula Support System General Weighted Mean by all of the Respondents:									4.25	GE
Instructional Support										
1. The school has adequate facilities, equipment in sports	3.95	HE	3.88	HE	4.17	HE	3.73	HE	3.9	HE
2. The instructional materials and teacher's manual were always available and	3.87	HE	3.88	HE	3.83	HE	4.00	HE	3.8	HE

provides modules for you for out of school approach										
3. The SHS faculty designed, selected, organized and used diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	4.03	HE	4.38	GE	4.22	GE	4.14	HE	4.19	HE
4. The SHS faculty monitored and evaluated learner progress and achievement using learner appropriate assessment tools.	3.97	HE	4.25	GE	4.33	GE	4.07	HE	4.15	HE
5. The SHS faculty communicated promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians.	3.99	HE	4.38	GE	3.72	HE	4.00	HE	4.02	HE
6. The SHS faculty provided timely and accurate feedback	4.13	HE	4.25	GE	4.28	GE	3.83	HE	4.12	HE
7. The teacher utilized assessment data to inform the modification of teaching and learning practices	4.16	HE	4.00	HE	4.28	GE	4.11	HE	4.13	HE
Instructional Support General Weighted Mean by all of the Respondents:									4.04	HE
Learning Competencies										
1. The learner's knowledge and skills in Safety and First Aid are applied in real life situation (First Aid)	4.34	GE	N/A	N/A	4.39	GE	4.32	GE	4.35	GE
2. The learners observed safety awareness to prevent untoward incident (First Aid)	4.18	HE	N/A	N/A	4.28	GE	4.29	GE	4.25	GE
3. The learners can discuss confidently the nature, purpose, procedure of movement screen for efficient and effective performance in different theories of motion (Human Movements)	4.13	HE	N/A	N/A	4.44	GE	4.10	HE	4.22	GE
4. The learners can explain clearly the	3.99	HE	N/A	N/A	4.44	GE	4.14	HE	4.19	HE

fundamental concepts and principles, proper communication techniques of coaching in relation to ethical standard and strategies in monitoring performance (Fundamentals of Coaching)											
5. The learners can identify surely how motivation, value of effective communication and group cohesion, arousal and anxiety affect sports performance and exercise participation (Psychological Aspect of Sports and Exercise)	3.91	HE	N/A	N/A	4.44	GE	4.29	GE	4.21	GE	
Learning Competencies											
Process Evaluation Statements	Alumni		Administrator		Faculty		Currently Enrolled Students		Overall Weighted Mean		
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	
6. The learners can distinguish truly the importance of test result as means of set fitness and can adjust training parameters according to training response (Fitness Testing Exercise Programming)	4.10	HE	N/A	N/A	4.28	GE	N/A	N/A	4.19	HE	
7. The learners can determine immediately the fundamental concept, principle, skills and mechanics of sports officiating, activity management and elements of an event plans (Sports Officiating Activity and Management)	4.03	HE	N/A	N/A	4.06	HE	N/A	N/A	4.04	HE	
8. The learners can demonstrate affectively the quality of leadership, safe and effective sports exercise, value and professional ethics in the conduct of fitness and	4.10	HE	N/A	N/A	4.11	HE	N/A	N/A	4.10	HE	

recreation activities (Fitness Sports and Recreation)										
Learning Competencies General Weighted Mean by all of the Respondents:									4.19	HE
Process Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean by all of the Respondents:									4.16	HE
Legend: "Not Implemented" (NI) - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" (PE) - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" (ME)- (2.60-3.39), "High Extent"(HE) - (3.40-4.19),										

The administrator did not give evaluation on the learning competencies domain, since they are not directly experienced or hands in with on it. It only included the faculty, currently enrolled and alumni, however, the currently enrolled students did not have evaluation on the statement no. 43, 44 and 45 since the statement topics are regarding the subject’s competencies that are offered on the 2nd semester. The data gathering was done a week before the 1st semester’s end and a week right after the semesterly break.

The curricula support system obtained general weighted mean of 4.25 and was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. However, the instructional support and the extent of implementation in the learning competencies obtained general weighted means of 4.04 and 4.19 and was interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation.

Process Evaluation provides information about the success or failure of the plan as it is being implemented and is conducted to help make changes to the plan selected/created during the input phase. The degree to which the program is being implemented as originally planned is also determined.

The grand weighted mean of the process evaluation of the study obtained 4.16 and interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation. This result of the study suggested that faculty should have continued trainings and seminars in the specialized subjects. The faculty who are teaching in the specific course/ specialized subject should be a master in that area of learning. This also implies the need to strengthen the extent of implementation of the seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies by releasing the learning materials and modules for the Sports Track Program specialized subjects and other budgets to allocate sports facilities and equipment in schools.

Product: *Extent of Implementation of the Attainment of Learning Outcomes in terms of Practicum, Work Immersion Program and Seven (7) Specialized Courses*

Table 18 on the next page shows the alumni’s responses on the implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum, work immersion program and seven (7) specialized courses. It can be gleaned from the table that statement namely; “The school provided safety learning environment for skills practice and development including the conduct tournament”, “The school provided learning environment for the learners to implements an existing sports and recreation program (for sports and recreation leader)”, “The school provided learning environment for the learner to employ stress management techniques to cope with training and competition demands”, “The work immersion provided choices for work that are relevant to your specialization”, “The learners developed a sound coaching philosophy”, “The learner completed a portfolio consisting of journals, work sheets, interview reports, reflection papers and information materials regarding the psychological benefits of regular sports and exercise participation”, “The learners administered accurately the appropriate basic exercise programs for different fitness and performance goals”, “The learners accomplished a comprehensive activity management portfolio”, and “The learners implemented the basic principle of fitness with confidence a short-term program in exercise/sports and recreation for a healthy individual or group” were interpreted to have a “Great Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.39, 4.33, 4.20, 4.29, 4.20, 4.31, 4.22, 4.27, and 4.33 respectively. On the other hand, 8 statements namely; “The

school provided learning environment for the learner to identify and apply the emerging trends in training, The school provided a general orientation for students and parents for the program on practicum and work immersion”, “The school required a parental consent for the work immersion program, “The partner industry is aligned in sports field”.

Table 18. Alumni Responses on the Implementation of the Attainment of Learning Outcomes in terms of Practicum, Work Immersion Program and Seven (7) Specialized Courses

Product Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
Frequency							
Practicum							
1. The school provided safety learning environment for skills practice and development including the conduct tournament	52	36	6	4	0	4.39	Great Extent
2. The school provided learning environment for the learners to implements an existing sports and recreation program (for sports and recreation leader)	48	37	10	3	0	4.33	Great Extent
3. The school provided learning environment for the learner to identify and apply the emerging trends in training	39	43	12	2	2	4.17	High Extent
4. The school provided learning environment for the learner to employ stress management techniques to cope with training and competition demands	41	39	15	3	0	4.20	Great Extent
Practicum General Weighted Mean by the Alumni:						4.27	Great Extent
Work Immersion							
1. The school provided a general orientation for students and parents for the program on practicum and work immersion	32	39	23	1	3	3.98	High Extent
2. The school required a parental consent for the work immersion program	39	40	15	3	1	4.15	High Extent
3. The work immersion provided choices for work that are relevant to your specialization	51	31	12	1	3	4.29	Great Extent
4. The partner industry is aligned in sports field	37	39	19	0	3	4.09	High Extent
Work Immersion General Weighted Mean by the alumni:						4.13	High Extent
(7) Specialized Courses							
1. You inculcated a safety practices consistently in sports, exercise and recreational activities.	40	37	16	2	3	4.11	High Extent
2. The learners administered the accurate movement screening.	34	48	14	0	2	4.14	High Extent
3. The learners designed a sound practice session.	34	40	20	4	0	4.06	High Extent
4. The learners developed a sound coaching philosophy.	45	34	14	4	1	4.20	Great Extent
5. The learner completed a portfolio consisting of journals, work sheets, interview reports, reflection papers and information materials regarding the psychological benefits of regular sports and exercise participation.	53	30	11	0	4	4.31	Great Extent
6. The learners administered accurately the appropriate basic exercise programs for different fitness and performance goals	44	39	11	1	3	4.22	Great Extent
7. The learner officiated with authority in interscholastic games/competitions.	41	38	11	5	3	4.11	High Extent
8. The learners accomplished a comprehensive activity	44	43	7	1	3	4.27	Great

management portfolio.								Extent
9. The learners implemented the basic principle of fitness with confidence a short-term program in exercise/sports and recreation for a healthy individual or group.	47	40	9	0	2	4.33		Great Extent
Learning Outcomes General Weighted Mean the Alumni:							4.19	High Extent
Overall Weighted Mean:							4.20	Great Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).								

“You inculcated a safety practices consistently in sports, exercise and recreational activities”, “The learners administered the accurate movement screening, The learners designed a sound practice sessions”, and “The learner officiated with authority in interscholastic games/competitions” were interpreted to have a “High Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.17, 3.98, 4.15, 4.09, 4.11, 4.14, 4.06, and 4.11 respectively.

The extent in practicum implementation obtained the overall mean of 4.27 and was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. However, the work immersion and learning outcome were interpreted to have “High Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained weighted mean of 4.13 and 4.19 respectively. In general, the overall weighted mean of 4.20 indicates that the assessment of the alumni respondents on the implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum, work immersion program and seven (7) specialized courses have a “Great Extent” level of implementation as assessed by the alumni respondents.

Table 19. Administrator’s Responses on the Implementation of the Attainment of Learning Outcomes in terms of Practicum and Work Immersion Program

Product Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
Frequency							
Practicum							
1. The school provided safety learning environment for skills practice and development including the conduct tournament	5	2	1	0	0	4.50	Great Extent
2. The school provided learning environment for the learners to implements an existing sports and recreation program (for sports and recreation leader)	5	2	1	0	0	4.50	Great Extent
3. The school provided learning environment for the learners to identify and apply the emerging trends in training	5	1	2	0	0	4.38	Great Extent
4. The school provided learning environment for the learners to employ stress management techniques to cope with training and competition demands	3	5	0	0	0	4.38	Great Extent
Practicum General Weighted Mean by the Administrator Respondents:						4.44	Great Extent
Work Immersion							
1. The school provided a general orientation for students and parents for the program on practicum and work immersion	6	1	1	0	0	4.63	Great Extent
2. The school required a parental consent for the work immersion program	6	1	1	0	0	4.63	Great Extent
3. The work immersion provided choices for work that are relevant to your specialization	5	1	2	0	0	4.38	Great Extent
4. The partner industry is aligned in sports field	5	3	0	0	0	4.63	Great

							Extent
Work Immersion General Weighted Mean by the Administrator:						4.57	Great Extent
Product Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean by the Administrator:						4.50	Great Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

Table 19 reveals the administrator’s responses on the implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum and work immersion program. It can be gleaned from the table that all of the statements namely, “The school provided safety learning environment for skills practice and development including the conduct tournament”, “The school provided learning environment for the learners to implements an existing sports and recreation program(for sports and recreation leader)”, “The school provided learning environment for the learners to identify and apply the emerging trends in training”, “The school provided learning environment for the learners to employ stress management techniques to cope with training and competition demands”, “The school provided a general orientation for students and parents for the program on practicum and work immersion”, “The school required a parental consent for the work immersion program”, “The work immersion provided choices for work that are relevant to your specialization and The partner industry is aligned in sports field”, were interpreted “Great Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.50, 4.50,4.38, 4.38, 4.63, 4.63, 4.38 and 4.63 respectively. The extent of practicum and work immersion were interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained weighted mean of 4.44 and 4.75 respectively. In general, the overall weighted mean of 4.5 indicates that the assessment of admin respondents on the implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum, work immersion program and seven (7) specialized courses have a “Great Extent” level of implementation as assessed by the admin respondents. It can be observed that administrator respondents had a positive attitude towards the extent of implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum and work immersion program.

Table 20 below shows below the faculty responses on the implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum, work immersion program and seven (7) specialized courses. It can be gleaned from the table that all the statements namely, “The school provided safety learning environment for skills practice and development including the conduct tournament”, “The school provided learning environment for the learners to implements an existing sports and recreation program (for sports and recreation leader)”, “The school provided learning environment for the learner to identify and apply the emerging trends in training, The school provided learning environment for the learner to employ stress management techniques to cope with training and competition demands”, “The learners designed a sound practice sessions”, “The learners developed a sound coaching philosophy”, “The learner completed a portfolio consisting of journals, work sheets, interview reports, reflection papers and information materials regarding the psychological benefits of regular sports and exercise participation”, “Thee learners administered accurately the appropriate basic exercise programs for different fitness and performance goals”, “The learners accomplished a comprehensive activity management portfolio” and “The learners implemented the basic principle of fitness with confidence a short-term program in exercise/sports and recreation for a healthy individual or group” were interpreted to have a “Great Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.39, 4.33, 4.39, 4.28, 4.33 4.33,4.22, 4.28, 4.44, 4.39, 4.28, 4.22 and 4.28 respectively. On the other hand, all statements namely, “The school provided a general orientation for students and parents for the program on practicum and work immersion”, “The partner industry is aligned in sports field”, “The learners administered the accurate movement screening” and “The learner officiated with authority in interscholastic games/competitions” were interpreted to have a “High Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.06, 4.17, 4.17 and 4.17 respectively.

Table 20. Faculty’s Responses on the Implementation of the Attainment of Learning Outcomes in terms of Practicum, Work Immersion Program and Seven (7) Specialized Courses

Product Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
Frequency							
Practicum							
1. The school provided safety learning environment for skills practice and development including the conduct tournament	8	9	1	0	0	4.39	Great Extent
2. The school provided learning environment for the learners to implements an existing sports and recreation program (for sports and recreation leader)	7	10	1	0	0	4.33	Great Extent
3. The school provided learning environment for the learner to identify and apply the emerging trends in training	9	8	0	1	0	4.39	Great Extent
4. The school provided learning environment for the learner to employ stress management techniques to cope with training and competition demands	8	9	0	0	1	4.28	Great Extent
Practicum General Weighted Mean by the Faculty Respondents:						4.35	Great Extent
Work Immersion							
1. The school provided a general orientation for students and parents for the program on practicum and work immersion	5	10	2	1	0	4.06	High Extent
2. The school required a parental consent for the work immersion program	7	10	1	0	0	4.33	Great Extent
3. The work immersion provided choices for work that are relevant to your specialization	8	9	0	1	0	4.33	Great Extent
4. The partner industry is aligned in sports field	5	12	0	1	0	4.17	High Extent
Work Immersion General Weighted Mean by the Faculty Respondents:						4.22	Great Extent
(7) Specialized Courses							
1. You inculcated a safety practices consistently in sports, exercise and recreational activities.	6	11	0	1	0	4.22	Great Extent
2. The learners administered the accurate movement screening.	5	12	0	1	0	4.17	High Extent
3. The learners designed a sound practice session.	8	9	0	0	1	4.28	Great Extent
4. The learners developed a sound coaching philosophy.	9	8	1	0	0	4.44	Great Extent
5. The learner completed a portfolio consisting of journals, work sheets, interview reports, reflection papers and information materials regarding the psychological benefits of regular sports and exercise participation.	8	9	1	0	0	4.39	Great Extent
6. The learners administered accurately the appropriate basic exercise programs for different fitness and performance goals	7	10	0	1	0	4.28	Great Extent
7. The learner officiated with authority in interscholastic games/competitions.	4	13	1	0	0	4.17	High Extent
8. The learners accomplished a comprehensive activity management portfolio.	6	10	2	0	0	4.22	Great Extent
9. The learners implemented the basic principle of fitness with confidence a short-term program in exercise/sports and recreation for a healthy individual or group.	6	11	1	0	0	4.28	Great Extent
Learning Outcomes General Weighted Mean by the Faculty Respondents:						4.27	Great

		Extent
Process Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean by the Faculty Respondents:	4.28	Great Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).		

The extent of practicum, work immersion and learning outcomes were interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained weighted mean of 4.35, 4.22 and 4.27 respectively. In general, the overall weighted mean of 4.28 indicates that the assessment of the faculty respondents on the implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum, work immersion program and seven (7) specialized courses have a “Great Extent” level of implementation. Table 21 below shows the currently enrolled students’ responses on the implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of seven (7) specialized courses. It can be gleaned from the table that the statements namely, “You inculcated a safety practices consistently in sports, exercise and recreational activities”, “You administered the accurate movement screening”, “You designed a sound practice sessions”.

Table 21. Currently Enrolled Students’ Responses on the Implementation of the Attainment of Learning Outcomes in Seven (7) Specialized Courses

Product Evaluation Statements	Great Extent	High Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not Implemented	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
Frequency							
(7) Specialized Courses							
1.You inculcated a safety practices consistently in sports, exercise and recreational activities.	90	82	21	14	0	4.20	High Extent
2.You administered the accurate movement screening.	64	98	33	11	1	4.03	High Extent
3.You designed a sound practice session.	70	78	47	10	2	3.99	High Extent
4.You developed a sound coaching philosophy.	72	87	36	9	3	4.04	High Extent
5.You completed a portfolio consisting of journals, work sheets, interview reports, reflection papers and information materials regarding the psychological benefits of regular sports and exercise participation.	95	73	35	3	1	4.25	Great Extent
Grand / Learning Outcomes General Weighted Mean by Currently Enrolled Students:						4.10	High Extent
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).							

“You developed a sound coaching philosophy” were interpreted to have a “High Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.20, 4.03, 3.99 and 4.04 respectively. On the other hand, statement which is “You completed a portfolio consisting of journals, work sheets, interview reports, reflection papers and information materials regarding the psychological benefits of regular sports and exercise participation” was interpreted to have a “Great Extent” level of implementation. These statements obtained the weighted mean of 4.25.

In general, the overall weighted mean of 4.10 indicates that the assessment of the currently enrolled student respondents on the implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of seven (7) specialized courses has a “High Extent” level of implementation.

However, almost all of the statements in the extent of attainment of learning outcomes in terms of seven (7) specialized Courses were interpreted by some of the alumni as “not implemented”.

The product evaluation statement namely; “The school provided safety learning environment for skills practice and development including the conduct of tournament” was interpreted to have “Great Extent” by admin, faculty and alumni. This statement obtained a weighted mean of 4.39, 4.50 and 4.39 respectively. The overall weighted mean obtained was 4.43 and was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. The statement namely; “The school provided learning environment for the learners to implements an existing sports and recreation program (for sports and recreation leader)” was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation by admin, faculty and alumni. This statement obtained a weighted mean of 4.33, 4.50 and 4.43. The overall weighted mean obtained was 4.43 and was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation.

Table 22. Summary of Responses on the Attainment of Learning Outcomes in terms of Practicum, Work Immersion Program and Seven (7) Specialized Courses

Product Evaluation Statements	Alumni		Administra tor		Faculty		Currently Enrolled Students		Overall Weighted Mean	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
Practicum										
1. The school provided safety learning environment for skills practice and development including the conduct tournament	4.39	GE	4.50	GE	4.39	GE	N/A	N/A	4.43	GE
2. The school provided learning environment for the learners to implements an existing sports and recreation program (for sports and recreation leader)	4.33	GE	4.50	GE	4.33	GE	N/A	N/A	4.3	GE
3. The school provided learning environment for the learner to identify and apply the emerging trends in training	4.17	HE	4.38	GE	4.39	GE	N/A	N/A	4.31	GE
4. The school provided learning environment for the learner to employ stress management techniques to cope with training and competition demands	4.20	GE	4.38	GE	4.28	GE	N/A	N/A	4.28	GE
Practicum General Weighted Mean by all of the Respondents:									4.33	GE
Work Immersion										
1. The school provided a general orientation for students and parents for the program on practicum and work immersion	3.98	HE	4.63	GE	4.06	HE	N/A	N/A	4.22	GE
2. The school required a parental consent for the work immersion program	4.15	HE	4.63	GE	4.33	GE	N/A	N/A	4.37	GE
3. The work immersion provided choices for work that are relevant to your specialization	4.29	GE	4.38	GE	4.33	GE	N/A	N/A	4.33	GE
4. The partner industry is aligned in sports field	4.09	HE	4.63	GE	4.17	HE	N/A	N/A	4.29	GE
5. The learner inculcated a safety practices consistently in sports, exercise and recreational activities.	4.11	HE	N/A	N/A	4.22	GE	4.20	GE	4.17	HE
Work Immersion General Weighted Mean by all of the Respondents:									4.29	HE
Learning Outcome of the Specialized Subjects										
1. The learners administered the	4.14	HE	N/A	N/A	4.17	HE	4.03	HE	4.11	HE

accurate movement screening. (Safety and First Aid)											
2. The learners designed a sound practice session. (Human Movement)	4.06	HE	N/A	N/A	4.28	GE	3.99	HE	4.11	HE	
3. The learners developed a sound coaching philosophy. (Fundamentals of Coaching)	4.20	GE	N/A	N/A	4.44	GE	4.04	HE	4.22	GE	
4. The learner completed a portfolio consisting of journals, work sheets, interview reports, reflection papers and information materials regarding the psychological benefits of regular sports and exercise participation. (Psychological Aspects of Sports and Exercise)	4.31	GE	N/A	N/A	4.39	GE	4.25	GE	4.31	GE	
5. The learners administered accurately the appropriate basic exercise programs for different fitness and performance goals (Testing and Exercise Programming)	4.22	GE	N/A	N/A	4.28	GE	N/A	N/A	4.25	GE	
6. The learner officiated with authority in interscholastic games/competitions. (Officiating activity Management)	4.11	HE	N/A	N/A	4.17	HE	N/A	N/A	4.14	HE	
7. The learners accomplished a comprehensive activity management portfolio. (Officiating Activity Management)	4.27	GE	N/A	N/A	4.22	GE	N/A	N/A	4.24	GE	
8. The learners implemented the basic principle of fitness with confidence a short-term program in exercise/sports and recreation for a healthy individual or group. (Sports and Recreation)	4.33	GE	N/A	N/A	4.28	GE	N/A	N/A	4.31	GE	
Learning Outcomes General Weighted Mean by all of the Respondents:									4.21	GE	
Product Evaluation Grand Weighted Mean by all of the Respondents:									4.27	GE	
Legend: "Not Implemented" - (1.0-1.79), "Poor Extent" - (1.80-2.59), "Moderate Extent" - (2.60-3.39), "High Extent" - (3.40-4.19), "Great Extent" - (4.20-5.00).											

Product evaluation provides information about whether the goals and objectives of the program have been met through those strategies designed/selected at the input level and adjusted through process level evaluation. The evaluation includes the extent of practicum, work immersion and 7 subjects learning outcomes.

The extent of practicum, work immersion and learning outcomes was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. This statement obtained weighted mean of 4.33, 4.29 and 4.21 respectively.

The overall weighted mean obtained was 4.27 and was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation. This result suggests the need to further strengthen the implementation of the practicum, work immersion and the learning outcome in each specialized subject by deploying the learners to the program aligned institution/ partner, ensuring the learning opportunity of the learners in their practicum and trained teachers to monitor students by having formative and summative assessment through learning outcome assessments.

Implications of the Findings

The significant findings of the study are summarized below:

Context Evaluation: *Extent of implementation of the program goals and objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program.*

Most of the respondent's assessment in the extent of the program goals and objectives of the Senior High School Sports Track Program were interpreted to have "Great Extent" level of implementation. Second, the respondents also agreed that the Philippine Education system through the Senior High School Sports Track Program is giving attention to the sports, physical education and health as a job opportunity. The administrators had positive attitude towards the goals and objectives of the senior high school sports track program. Generally, context evaluation was interpreted to have "Great Extent" level of implementation. However, it can be gleaned that statements namely: "The program discusses various factors that affect social, psychological, and cognitive development in sports leadership and management," "The program designed to facilitate lifelong learning for the learners" and "The program empowered the learners to be competent and be harmonize in local and global communities" had the lowest emphasis by the alumni and currently enrolled students. It can also be observed that item "The program reinforced the learner's interest to career opportunities" has the lowest emphasis by the faculty.

Input Evaluation: *Extent of implementation of the Program Plan in internal and external stakeholder support, societal support (Partner and Linkages) and administrative support.*

The extent of the internal and external support was interpreted by all of the respondents to have "High Extent" of implementation. However, it can be observed that the statements namely: "Parents participated in planning activity in off campus through PTA meeting," "Learner's Resources are available in the school like books and module related the Sports Track Program," and "The school provided adequate facilities and equipment," turn out to be in the bottom three of the lowest emphasis. Second, the result of the societal support is also interpreted to have "High Extent" of Implementation. However, it can be seen from the statements namely: "The company/ institution partner of the school is aligned in the sports track program" "Your school enter partnership in sports track in Fitness Ships, Gym and Sports Club" and "School and Industry collaboration is strong which ensure the meaningful practicum" had the lowest emphasis. The extent of administrative support was assessed by the administrator to have a "Great Extent" of implantation. However, the rest of the respondents agreed that the program administrative support have only "High Extent" of implementation. Generally, input evaluation was interpreted to have "Great Extent" level of implementation.

Process Evaluation: *Extent of implementation of seven (7) specialized courses in terms of curricula support system, instructional support and learning competencies.*

The Curricula Support was evaluated by the respondents to have a "Great Extent" of implementation, however, it can be gleaned from the table that statements namely: "The SHS faculty applied a range of appropriate strategies that maintain learning environment that motivate learning to for productively," "The SHS faculty planned managed and implemented developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts," and "The SHS faculty managed the learner's behavior constructively by applying positive and nonviolent discipline" had the lowest emphasis by the alumni. However, the extent of instructional support was evaluated to have "High Extent" level of implementation, however, it can be gleaned from statements namely: "The school has adequate facilities, equipment in sports," "The instructional materials and teacher's manual were always available and provides modules for you for out of school approach," and "The SHS faculty monitored and evaluated learner progress and achievement using learner appropriate assessment tools" had the lowest emphasis. In Learning competencies domain, it can be gleaned from the table that statement namely: "The learners can identify surely how motivation, value of effective communication and group cohesion, arousal and anxiety affect sports performance and exercise participation (Psychological Movement) and (Human Movement)," "The learners can

determine immediately the fundamental concept, principle, skills and mechanics of sports officiating, activity management and elements of an event plans” had the lowest emphasis. All the respondents agreed that faculty teaching in specialized subject in the program were licensed and are sports practitioner. Generally, process evaluation was interpreted to have “Great Extent” level of implementation.

Product Evaluation: *Extent of implementation of the attainment of learning outcomes in terms of practicum, work immersion program and seven (7) specialized courses.*

The extent of practicum implementation was interpreted generally to have “Great Extent” of implementation. Also, the extent of work immersion implementation was interpreted to have “Great Extent” by the administrator however it was evaluated by the alumni and faculty to only have “High Extent” level of implementation, moreover, it can be gleaned that the statements “The school provided a general orientation for students and parents for the program on practicum and work immersion” and “Partner industry is aligned in sports field” had the lowest emphasis. The extent of achieving the learning outcome was evaluated generally to have “Great Extent” of Implementation, however there are statements that were interpreted by the alumni to have “High Extent” of implementation. The statements namely: “You inculcated a safety practices consistently in sports, exercise and recreational activities (First Aid),” “The learners administered the accurate movement screening (Human Movements),” “The learners developed a sound coaching philosophy (Fundamentals of Coaching)” had the lowest emphasis.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the item with the low emphasis as shown in the study, the following are conclusions:

Context Evaluation

Stipulated from the Dep Ed memo no. 4 s. 2014 (Senior High School and Its Curriculum Requirements), the aim of the Senior High school program is to develop holistic learner with 21st century skills, prepared for higher education, middle level skills development, employment and entrepreneurship. However, the alumni viewed that the program did not emphasize the alignment in sports development leadership, program design towards lifelong learners and its empowerment to develop the learners to be more competent. Faculty members who are teaching the program stressed that there is only limited career for the students after they graduated. Students who are currently enrolled in the program viewed that the program did not emphasize the relevance of the content in the field of work. Since every first-born curriculum is not perfectly implemented, some of the alumni or first batch of graduates viewed that there were statements that were not implemented.

Input Evaluation

The parents of the alumni respondents were informed regarding the school activities aligned with the program however, there was a failure to convene for a meeting/orientation and they were not involved in the planning. Most of the DepEd schools look into partnership and linkages with a sports institution to fill up the insufficiency of the school sports facilities. Insufficient facilities and teachers are the reasons Rizal Technology University (RTU) decided to discontinue the Sports Track offering starting next school year. The University of Makati is the pioneering school that offers the program and maintained better facilities compared to other schools. Based from the alumni assessment regarding the alignment of partner institutions of the program, it was found out that most of the schools have low compliance in following the DepEd Order no.30, s. 2017 (Work Immersion Guidelines and Senior High School Curriculum Guide in Practicum Courses) As stipulated from the DepEd order no. 30 s. 2017 (The Guidelines in Work Immersion and Senior High School Curriculum Guide in Practicum Courses) only fitness shops, gym, sports club are considered aligned institutions in the program. However, Vito L. Belarmino -SHS (Jose P. Laurel, Sr. JHS) in Quezon City Division focused in a partnership with Health Care Advantage Institute that conduct trainings in EMS or Emergency Medical Service and Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA)

Accreditations for NCII. Alumni respondents experienced the inadequacy of budget in terms of insufficient instructional materials and sports facilities. The alumni respondents are not aware that they had insurance during immersion for their safety and security.

Process Evaluation

Alumni respondents stressed that the program did not emphasize the class room instruction specifically regarding the appropriateness of strategies that maintain learning environment to be productive, planning and implementing developmentally sequenced in teaching in meeting curriculum requirements contexts and in managing behavior of learners constructively. To sum up, based from the alumni assessment, the readiness of the teachers as well as the school toward sports track program implementation is somewhat constrained. Curriculum guides in specialized subjects are already available, however, the modules and instructional materials are still in process and yet to be released. On the other hand, the teachers must be innovative to develop appropriate assessment tools fitted to the course standard and competencies.

Product Evaluation

Sports track students are partially equipped to officiate sports event in an interscholastic games/competition unless they trained and are accredited from specific sports event federations. All of the respondents perceived that the program did not emphasize consistency to inculcate the safety practices in sports and recreational activities. Physical Education Teachers who have specialization in First Aid and Human Movements subjects are limited.

Recommendations

In the view of the foregoing conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

Context Evaluation

Implementing Guidelines on the Special Program in Sports to offer SPS (Special Program in Sports) to have continual sports development and a career pathing for the learners. For the stand-alone Senior High Schools/Colleges that currently offer a Sports Track Program without a Junior High School, it is recommended for the school to tie up with a Junior High School to help them in meeting the requirements of the Dep Ed order no. 25 s. 2015 (Implementing Guidelines on the Special Program in Sports) to offer SPS (Special Program in Sports). Students who graduated from the special program of sports in Junior High School must be prioritized and accepted for the Sports Track Program in Senior High School. To the graduates of a non-special program in sports who will pursue the Sports Track Program in Senior High School, they must undergo written and performance assessments aligned with the Special Program in Sports competencies. Students who graduated from the Sports Track Program in Senior High School must be prioritized and accepted to the courses related to physical education, fitness, sports, sports science, BPE Program (teaching) in tertiary level. To the graduates of a non-sports track program who will pursue the courses related to physical education, fitness and sports in tertiary level, they must write and performance assessments aligned with the Senior High School Sports Track competencies. It is recommended to have a full implementation of DepEd order no. 41 s. 2014 (Senior High School Career Guidance Program and Early Registration) to strengthen the awareness of the Sports Track Program students to their ideal exit and career opportunities.

Input Evaluation

Implementing Guidelines of Off Campus Activity. There must be a full implementation of the DepEd Memo no. 82, s. 2011 (Learning Resources Management System Implementation in Rationalization DepEd Structure) to make the learning materials and modules for the specialized subjects in the Senior High School Sports Program available. Schools that offer the Sports Track Program must have adequate facilities needed in the classroom instructions and sports- related discussion, it is recommended to have maximum of 45 students in each class as stated in DepEd Memo no. 4 s. 2014 (Senior High School Curriculum and Its Requirements) As stated in DepEd

Memo no. 4 s. 2014 (Senior High School and Its Curriculum Requirements) the minimum requirements for a school that wants to offer the Sports Track Program is to have standard track and field oval and standard equipment in track in field sports event. As stated in DepEd Order no. 25 s. 2015 (Implementing Guidelines in Special Program in Sports), the school must have access to the standard equipment and facilities available in the community especially those contained in physical facilities manual and International Specifications like track and field oval, gym/covered court, basketball and volleyball court, swimming pool, football, softball, baseball field, spacious playing area and another sports equipment must be met. DepEd schools must conduct benchmarking of the standard facilities in classroom learning instructions in pioneer schools. It is recommended to maintain a strong partnership among the partner institutions and linkages that are aligned in the program for the work immersion, as stipulated in DepEd Order no. 40, s. 2015 (K to 12 Partnership). It is recommended to conduct continued training for faculty in their specific area of specialization as stated in DepEd Order no. 42 s. 2017 (National Adaptation and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers). School administrators must revisit DepEd Orders as part of their comprehensive re-orientation for them to enhance the Sports Program implementation.

Process Evaluation

Guidelines on the allocation Delivery and Distribution of Instructional Materials to Support the K-12 Curriculum and DepEd Order No. 039 s. 2018 (Additional Information and Clarification to DepEd Order no. 30 s. 2017). It is recommended to have a full compliance of DepEd Order no. 3 s. 2016 (Hiring guidelines of Senior High School Teachers). It is recommended to have a full compliance of parent/teacher conference in assessing students' performance and needs. To strengthen the program implementation in terms of its curricula and instructional support, it is recommended that the faculty members who are teaching in specialized subjects in the program be required to enroll in a graduate school aligned in sports, physical education, first aid and fitness. Another recommendation, is the availability of a scholarship grant to the faculty members who are required to enroll in the graduate school aligned in sports, physical education, first aid and fitness.

Product Evaluation

There should be budget allocation from Maintenance, Operations and Overhead Expenditures (MOOE) for the students' training and certification in officiating and coaching in the specific sports federation as well as NC II accreditation in Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) for Emergency Medical Services (EMS). It is recommended to allow science, health teachers or any related courses to teach in Human Movement and First Aid courses in the program in the absence of physical education teachers who specialized in the courses. Schools that offer Sports Track Program must have aligned partner institution or sports related partner as stated in DepEd Order 30 s. 2017 (The Guidelines in Work Immersion and Senior High School Curriculum Guide in Practicum Courses), Schools must conduct orientation for the students, parents and partner institutions, to assure the safety of the students and to address all the concern in the work immersion as stated in DepEd Order no. 30 s. 2017 (The Guidelines in Work Immersion and Senior High School Curriculum Guide in Practicum Courses). It is recommended to include First Aid/ EMS (Emergency Medical Service) institutions as aligned partner in the program in DepEd Order no. 30 s. 2017 (The Guidelines in Work Immersion and Senior High School Curriculum Guide in Practicum Courses). Schools should avail insurance for students during work immersions as stipulated in DepEd Order no. 30 s. 2017 (The Guidelines in Work Immersion and Senior High School Curriculum Guide in Practicum Courses).

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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